

CONSIDERATIONS ON THE ECOLOGY AND SPREAD OF THE SPECIES *REYNOUTRIA JAPONICA* HOUTT IN THE BISTRITA RIVER BASIN - FIRST NOTE

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Abstract

This contribution aims to provide a brief overview of the spread of *Reynoutria japonica* Houtt. plant species in the Bistrita River basin. The paper is part of a larger study that refers to the impact of the most aggressive non-native plants in the Bistrita basin. Our goal is to study and record the presence, distribution and impact of these non-native plant species. The study took place along the entire Bistrita River basin and on the valleys of its main tributaries. This non-native species of Asian origin has experienced an explosive spread in the last decade in many areas of Romania. In the studied area it proves to be particularly aggressive with the riparian areas where it settles. The spread of this species is attributed to several factors that we will discuss here. *Reynoutria japonica* Houtt. causes major losses from an economic point of view but primarily from a biodiversity point of view.

Keywords: Bistrita River basin, *Reynoutria japonica*, wet meadows, anthropization, non-native species, riparian habitats.

INTRODUCTION

Invasive species are currently recognized as one of the world's major threats to biodiversity [1] and to the structure and functions of native ecosystems [2]. The uncontrolled spread of invasive, non-native plant species is one of the most pressing nature conservation issues of this century [3]. Alien or non-native plants have a rapidly adapting behavior to new territories and climates so that they can become dominant; they become aggressive for the colonized, habitats, **invasive** plant species. The term invasive plant (invasive plant species) is one established for this type of species in the literature [3].

Non-native species invasiveness is so pressing at the international level nowadays that a working international group has been set up to investigate this complex and current issue that requires urgent solutions (Invasive Species Specialist Group (ISSG)), [1].

These plant species alter native habitats, leading to the replacement of native species. Species diversity decreases as a direct effect of this "invasion." This leads to the loss of biodiversity, at least locally, due to competition from these invasive species. Non-native species compete for resources (space, light, water and nutrients), suppressing the growth of native ones, mainly by occupying land and blocking sunlight.

The Bistrita River basin is one of the largest River basins in the Eastern Carpathians - Romania. The surface of the basin is about 7039 km² [4], (figure 1).

Bistrita or Moldavian Bistrita River is located in the historical province of Moldova, in the North-East area of Romania and has a total length of 283 km. Of this length, over 65% is across a mountainous area. It is a right tributary of the Siret River and flows into it downstream of the city of Bacau. Its source is in the Rodna Mountains, below the Gărgălău peak.

We chose this basin area for our study because it is an important River and especially because its basin is located predominantly in the mountainous area with a high degree of anthropization. This area has undergone major changes in the last 60 years and in the last 20 years, anthropization has visibly accelerated.

There is a small number of studies on the presence and impact of invasive species in the Bistrita River basin. In the latest studies, there are some relevant data that will help us understand the ecology, biology and negative impact of this species on local biodiversity. It is very difficult to estimate at least from an economic point of view the real damage caused to the natural environment by the spread of this species [5]. There are several studies we mention here. The most recent have been published in [6, 7, 3, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 5].

Fig. 1. Delimitation of the Bistrita River basin on the Romanian territory. *Author source*

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The data used in this study were collected from 2008 to the present (2021) during several field trips, covering the studied basin area. The riparian habitats located on the Bistrita

River valley as well as on the valleys of the main tributaries were visually inspected by the method of transects. The ruderal, anthropized, or transformed areas near the localities were also studied. Field observations were made in spring, summer, and autumn (during vegetative period).

During these field trips, biological materials were collected for identification (plants and parts of plants) which are stored and preserved in the Scientific Collection of the Museum of Natural Sciences in Piatra Neamt.

In order to identify the vegetal material was used the identification key from [14]. The maps in figures 1 and 2 were created using the ArcGIS 10.6 software. The map in figure 2 represents the territorial spread of the populations of *Reynoutria japonica* Houtt. mapped by the authors from [5], later completed with new data from the field. The GPS positions of the locations and the spatial coverage areas of these populations were also identified in order to further study their evolution over time. A series of documentary photographs were taken. Smartphones and portable GPS devices were also used for this purpose.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Reynoutria japonica Houtt. plant species (syn. *Fallopia japonica* (Houtt.) Ronse Decr., *Polygonum cuspidatum* Sieb. et Zucc.) - photos 3-8. Geophytic floristic element, adventitious plant, allochthonous, invasive, $2n = 44$, general appearance photo no. 7. Native species from East Asia (Vietnam, Japan, Sakhalin region, Russia, Korea, and China), [15, 16, 17]).

It was introduced in Europe to be used as an ornamental plant [18]. Gradually, the species became known throughout the continent as an adventitious plant, decorative in shape and color. The species is very plastic from an ecological and geographical point of view; it is edible in the young stage (non-lignified shoots) and also a honey producing plant.

It was introduced in Romania in parks and botanical/private gardens from where the plant got out of control being declared sub-spontaneous and later invasive. In the year 2000 it was registered in over 137 populations across the country [12, 13]. The species has been classified as "highly invasive" - extremely invasive by the CABI Invasive Species Compendium [2 websites].

The historical records of the distribution of the species in the Bistrita River basin come from the following bibliographical sources: [19] - Maramures County; [20, 21, 12] - Harghita and Neamt counties; [22, 23, 24, 25, 26, 27, 28, 29, 30, 12] - Suceava County.

The recent records marked on the map in figure 2 (with a star icon) were made by [5], completed with [31], doc. : Hemeius, Buda (Bacau County), Piatra Neamt - in the city center, Precista and near the River Bistrita, Hamzoaia, Tasca, Telec, Gherman, Bicaz, Stejaru, Tarcau, Brates, Bicaz Chei, Bicazu Ardelean, Agarcia, Alexandru cel Bun, Lunca, Madei, Farcasa, Borca, Frumosu, Galu, Poiana Teiului, Poiana Largului, Chiriteni, Buhalnita, Potoci, Bicaz, Secu, Piraul Mare, Ceahlau, Poiana, Bradu, Topolniceni, (Neamt County); Neagra Sarului, Sarisor, Panaci, Todireni, Rosu, Praleni, Pilugani, Argestru, Iacobeni, Ciocanești, Vatra-Dornei, Dorna Arini - Ortoaia, Rusca, Sunatori, Chiril, Holda, Holdita, Satu Mare, Crucea, Brosteni, Pietroasa (Suceava County).

R. japonica invades not only riparian habitats and roadsides with high humidity but also semi-natural mountain meadows with a high to average productivity. This phenomenon of invasion was encountered in Ceahlau and Bistricioara, near Durau in Neamt County [5].

This is one of the species that greatly affects the natural environment, the riparian habitats in this area being threatened. The populations of this species are continuously expanding from the

banks of the main River to the lower reaches, reproducing mainly vegetatively. Currently, the populations of this species are out of control and occupy considerable areas on the river banks and the major riverbeds of some tributaries. The colonies have areas between 0.5 and 100 m².

It is extremely worrying that the fact, although visible, these vegetal formations are not taken into account, or considered a threat by any environmental authorities. The species are constantly spreading on both degraded lands and wet pastures in the meadows of the Bistrita River and its tributaries. It is present on the territory of Ceahlau National Park and in Bicaz Gorges - Hasmas National Park.

This species, once installed, gradually replaces native herbaceous plant species [13]. *Reynoutria japonica* has a major impact on invaded ecosystems and sometimes irreversibly affects the genetic and specific diversity of the area. Following field observations, it was found that only native developed specimens of *Salix sp.* and *Alnus sp.* resists shading. The species has an extremely high adaptation to different soil types [13]. Climate change and global warming, which has become evident in the last 10 years, may become a driving factor in accelerating its spread within the Bistrita River basin.

Regarding the hybrid species *Reynoutria x bohemica* (Chrték et Chrtkova) (*Fallopia x bohemica* (Chrték et Chrtkova) registered by [28]; we did not encounter this hybrid species in our study area.

Initially, the species was cultivated and got out of control on modified, marginal and ruderal lands. From the gardens, it was spread involuntarily with the vegetal remains thrown uncontrollably on the marginal lands, dumpsites, disturbed terrain by construction works (excavations, leveling, etc.). This kind of areas has visibly multiplied on the riverbeds, thus an almost ideal ecological niche has been created for this species. Due to the anthropization and disturbance of natural habitats, the species is expanding. “Without interventions on natural habitats, invasive species have little chance to affect a native, ecologically stable ecosystem” [32, 33]. “*Reynoutria japonica* has the ability to completely replace indigenous plant communities in large areas by shading [30,28]. It also has the ability to maintain a certain balance in the ecosystem by changing resources, leaving native species unlikely to compete with them” [34]. The dense communities composed by these species (photos 1-5) shade the soil and “reduce by up to 90% the incident solar radiation” [13].

Photo 1. *Reynoutria japonica* - Red Lake.
Author source.

Photo 2. *Reynoutria japonica* consistent population on the bank of Bistrita River.
Author source.

Photo 3. *Reynoutria japonica*, installed on a disturbed ground. *Author source.*

Photo 4. *Reynoutria japonica* winter appearance, Piatra Neamt city. *Author source.*

Photo 5. *Reynoutria japonica* look at flowering time. *Author source.*

Photo 6. *Reynoutria japonica* shape of the mature leaf (back). *Author source.*

CONCLUSIONS

Thanks to high adaptability on an extremely dynamic ecological niche, *Reynoutria japonica* Houtt. occupies more and more territory in the Bistrita River basin. The number but also the size of the studied colonies increase from year to year.

This phenomenon occurs through the occupation of the land and the loss of biodiversity, limiting or even stopping the useful productivity of native plants that are part of the natural composition of wet meadows.

The pressure exerted on the native habitats is of great importance because, in the Bistrita River basin mostly located in the mountain area, the useful lands are a limited resource.

Fig. 2. Localities where the species *Reynoutria japonica* Houtt. was reported. Author source.

If the current trend of propagation is maintained, we may witness in the near future serious and even irreversible damage to the native riparian habitats. Thus, the useful agricultural areas (wet pastures and hayfields) are in real danger of being colonized and affected at least partially by this species.

The phenomenon of climate change, rather evident in recent years can become an important factor in the spread of this species. *Reynoutria japonica* could benefit from global warming of the future and could expand in the adjacent mountain valleys of the tributaries, at higher altitudes. The climatic stratification (under a normal thermal regime) currently plays the role of a natural protective barrier. From the analyzed data it was found that any population of *Reynoutria japonica* Houtt. is located at an altitude above 1000 meters.

The novelty of this study consists of highlighting the phenomenon of this species extension in the Bistrita River basin. A number of 60 new populations of *Reynoutria japonica*

Houtt. were identified. There is an obvious expansion of this species from only 13 populations mentioned before.

Anthropization and the degree of change in soil structure play a decisive role in the speed with which this species spreads on the studied territory.

The impact on the productivity of the invaded habitats as well as the productivity of this species in the Bistrita River basin will be investigated in further fieldwork.

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